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AUDIT REPORT AND ITS ELEMENTS

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Abstract. In all developed countries, those who want to become an accountant-auditor face many years of study and practice, as well as many exams. Public associations of auditors regularly monitor the activities of auditing organizations and the quality of their services in foreign countries.

Key words: audit, socio-economic development, index, sub-index, period, regions.

INTRODUCTION

The audit report represents the result of the audit. The process of preparing an audit report is one of the main challenges faced by auditors. The complexity of interpreting the requirements of international audit standards creates problems in the formation of an audit opinion. In this context, it is important to develop and implement effective methods and tools aimed at solving these problems. The principles of transparency, reliability and compliance with legal requirements should always be kept relevant in the process of presenting the audit report. These and a number of other reasons require appropriate training, skills, experience and knowledge. The opinion that the financial statement is prepared in all important aspects in accordance with the basis used for its preparation is an instrument that allows to increase the efficiency of the capital market and to evaluate and predict the consequences of various economic decisions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The auditor's report is a document drawn up based on the results of the audit. It is this document that confirms whether the financial report of the client company is correctly drawn up in all important respects or otherwise. Also, through the financial report and audit report, companies can attract investors, get loans from banks or international financial institutions at low rates. In this regard, the audit report confirms the continuity of the enterprise's activities and the reliability of its financial statements.

Due to the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 25, 2021 "On Auditing Activities", a mandatory rule on the application of international standards of auditing came into force on the territory of our country. According to this law, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan is entrusted with the authority to determine the procedure for recognizing the text of the international audit standards in the state language. In order to ensure the execution of the task defined by the law "On the procedure for recognizing international auditing standards for use in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated April 11, 2022 No. 171 was developed. According to this regulation, the translation of the text of the international auditing standards into the national language is entrusted to the Chamber of Auditors of Uzbekistan. Also, the Chamber of

Auditors of Uzbekistan will have to submit the translated text to the International Federation of Accountants, based on the conclusion of the expert commission established by the Ministry of Economy and Finance of Uzbekistan on its conformity with the English text.

It is stated that "A document containing the written opinion of the audit organization on the reliability of the financial report and compliance with the legal requirements on accounting is an audit report" ¹.

The content and formalization procedure of the auditor's conclusion on the financial report and the requirements for it are regulated by the international audit standard No. 700 entitled "Forming an opinion and drawing up a conclusion on the financial report". Also, No. 701 entitled "Providing information on important issues of the audit in the audit report", No. 705 entitled "Modification of the opinion in the audit report", No. 706 entitled "Explanatory paragraph and other illustrative paragraphs in the audit report" are also used in issuing the audit report. . In accordance with the above-mentioned standards, it is determined that the audit report will be formalized in the following ways (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Form of audit report²

So, in accordance with the international standards of auditing, there are two types of audit conclusions: unmodified and modified audit conclusions. An unmodified auditor's report is issued when the financial statements are free from material misstatement in all material respects.

A foreigner scientists A. Arens and Dj. Lobbeck about the auditor's conclusion, ³they say "the auditor's conclusion based on the results of the inspection".

F.L. Defliz, G.R. Djenik, V.M. O'Reilly, M.B. According to the Hirschs , they reacted to the auditor's conclusion as "the opinion issued on the result of the audit" ⁴.

L.A. Yuditseva describes the auditor's opinion ⁵as "the auditor's opinion, according to its content, is the auditor's professional opinion on the reliability of accounting reports. "

¹Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan " On audit activity". No. LRU-677. <https://lex.uz/docs/5702566>

²It was prepared by the author on the basis of international auditing standards.

³ Arens , AA Auditing and Assurance Services: An Integrated Approach. Pearson. 2013, pg 65.

⁴ Audit Montgomery / F. L. Deflis , G. R. Djenik , V. M. O'Reilly , M. B. Hirsch i dr . / pod ed . Ya.V. Sokolova. M.: Audit, YUNITI, 1997. 542 p. .

⁵Yuditseva L.A. Razvitie methodicheskogo obespecheniya formirovaniya auditorskogo zaklyuchenia o bukhgalterskoy (financial) otchetnosti. - abstract dissertation na soiskanie uchenoy stepi candida ekonomicheskikh nauk. 2014 str. 10 .

, commented on the audit report that "it is a general collection of data, information and audit evidence collected during the audit, and it is compiled into a general volume and stitched to it according to the sequence of these data."⁶

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2023, a total of 6,614 audit opinions were issued, of which 5,814 or 87.9% were positive audit opinions, 681 or 10.3% were opinions with comments, and 113 or 1.7% were negative opinions. , commenting on 6 or 0.1 percent constitutes a conclusion in the form of rejection.

To form an opinion on the conclusion of the audit of financial statements, the auditor must use professional judgment to obtain reasonable assurance that the financial statements are free from material misstatement. For this, the auditor should pay attention to the following factors (Figure 2):

Figure 2. Factors affecting the formation of the auditor's conclusion ⁷.

It is desirable to have a certain consistency in the form and content of the audit report, because it helps to achieve credibility in the international financial market and helps the user to understand the report and unusual situations when they occur.

The audit report is formulated in writing and includes the following sections (Table 1).

⁶Koziev I.N. Issues of drawing up audit reports and conclusions on the results of audit inspections. / "Economy and innovative technologies" scientific electronic journal. No. 4, July-August, 2015.

⁷ The author by t is tricked .

Table 1

Follow-up of the audit report

The main sections of the auditor's report	Description
Title	The audit report must have a title, that is, it must be clearly indicated that this document is the conclusion of an independent auditor.
Addressee	Usually, the addressee of the audit opinion is determined by law, in most cases the addressee may be shareholders or persons responsible for corporate management.
Introduction	This would be a statement that states the name of the company that is being audited, the dates of the financial period that the audit covers, which is usually the fiscal year.
Opinion	<p>In this paragraph, a brief description of the audited organization, the audited financial statements, the names of the financial statements, the rules of the accounting policy and other explanatory materials, as well as the period and dates of the financial statements are indicated.</p> <p>If the auditor provides an unmodified audit opinion on financial statements prepared in accordance with the concept of reliable representation, one of the following statements should be included in the opinion (both statements are equally valid):</p> <p><i>" In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements are presented fairly in all material respects in accordance with [applicable financial reporting framework]"</i></p> <p><i>"In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements are presented [...] fairly and reliably in accordance with the [applicable financial reporting framework]."</i></p>
Responsibilities of directors and auditors	This section clearly states the responsibilities of the directors of the company being audited, and the responsibilities of the auditor. It states that the management and directors of the company accept the duty of providing the auditor with all the financial documentation required for the audit. It also states that the documentation provided is true and accurate to the best of the director's knowledge. It is stated that the auditor's role is to audit the financial statements given by the company. It also states that the auditor must form his opinion based on the information provided.
Basis of opinion	In the auditor's report, after the "Opinion" section, the "Basis for opinion" section should be indicated separately. This paragraph: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a statement that the audit was conducted in accordance with international audit standards; - include a link to the section of the audit report describing the audit obligations in accordance with international audit standards; - a statement that the auditor is independent from the organization in accordance with the relevant ethical requirements used in the audit and that he has fulfilled other ethical obligations of the auditor in accordance with these requirements;

	- includes statements about whether or not the auditor believes that the evidence gathered is sufficient and appropriate for the auditor's opinion.
Going concern	If the auditors believe that a material uncertainty exists, they should describe it in a separate "Material uncertainty about going concern" section.
The main issues of the audit	In cases where the entity undergoing audit is registered on the stock exchange or required by law, the important issues for the audit should be reflected in this section in accordance with the professional judgment of the auditors.
Other information	If the auditors received other information during the audit, they should reflect it in the "Other information" section.
Responsible for financial reporting	This section describes the responsibilities of corporate governance and preparers of financial statements.
Auditor's responsibility for auditing financial statements	This section describes the auditor's objective, whether misstatements are due to error or fraud, and the "importance" that the auditor uses professional judgment and professional skepticism during the audit.
Obligation to prepare other reports	If the auditor is obliged to prepare other reports in accordance with the legislation, this obligation should be reflected in the section entitled "Report in accordance with the requirements of other legislation and regulatory documents".
Name of the head of the task responsible for the audit task	The name of the head of the audit engagement is indicated, except in cases where his personal safety is at risk.
Auditor's signature	The conclusion must have the auditor's signature.
Address of the auditing organization	The address of the audit organization is displayed
The date of the audit report	The term of the auditor's report cannot be earlier than the date on which the auditor gathers sufficient and appropriate evidence to support his opinion on the financial statements.

It should be noted that all these elements may not be reflected in the summary of the auditor's report, in particular "name", "Addressee", "Opinion", "Reasons for the opinion", "Responsible for the financial statement", "Responsibility of the auditor for the audit of the financial statement", "Sections where the name of the head of the task responsible for the audit assignment, "Signature of the auditor", "Address of the audit organization", "Date of the audit report" must be reflected in the mandatory order, the "Main issues of the audit" section is listed or required by law if available, the section "Other information" is reflected by the auditor when other information is available, and the section "Continuity of activity" when necessary.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were reached regarding issues related to formalization of the auditor's report:

1. Strengthen audit quality control. external quality control of auditing organizations and the mechanisms of quality control of auditors' work should be improved. It is considered appropriate to

strengthen internal control, increase requirements for professional training of auditors, and use new technologies in audit practice.

2. Regular, consistent organization of training and professional development of auditors will eliminate possible errors and deficiencies in the formation and formalization of audit conclusions.

3. Audit organizations to improve their audit methodology. It is necessary to develop more effective audit methods that allow a more complete and accurate assessment of the compliance of financial reporting with current standards. This can certainly be achieved through the use of advanced analytical methods, as well as a deeper analysis of the company's business processes.

4. Authorized bodies regulating audit activities should actively work on improving the legislation in the field of audit and financial reporting. By improving the mechanisms of state control over the activities of auditing firms and increasing accountability for violations of auditing standards and requirements, the quality of financial audits will improve and confidence in financial statements will increase.

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